

Analysis of the Effect of Fundamental Factors and Consumer Price Index on Company Stock Returns (Study on the Consumer Goods Industry Sector Listed on the IDX for the Period 2016 – 2021)

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Abstract:- This study aims to analyze the effect of fundamental factors (return on assets, debt to asset ratio, quick ratio, total asset turnover) and consumer price index on company stock returns in the consumer goods industry sector. The population in this study were 63 companies in the consumer goods industry sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2016 – 2021. The sampling method used was purposive sampling with a total sample of 35 companies. The data analysis method used in this research is panel data regression. The results of the study found that the return on assets had a significant effect on the company's stock returns, the debt to asset ratio had a significant effect on the company's stock returns, the quick ratio had a significant effect on the company's stock returns, the consumer price index had a significant effect on the company's stock returns, while the total asset turnover had no effect. significant to the company's stock return. The results of the research simultaneously show that Return on Assets (ROA), Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR), Quick Ratio (QR), Total Asset Turnover (TATO), and Consumer Price Index (CPI) have a significant effect on company stock returns.

Keywords:- Return on Assets (ROA), Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR), Quick Ratio (QR), Total Asset Turnover (TATO), and Consumer Price Index (CPI).

I. INTRODUCTION

The consumer goods industry sector is one of the main sectors of choice for investors to invest because the shares of companies in this industry still offer upward potential. This industry also tends to survive the crises that occur because it is an industry to meet the daily needs needed by the community. The consumer goods industry sector still plays a significant role in Indonesia's industry and economy. From data reported by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), in 2016 the consumer goods industry had a role in Indonesia's GDP of 5.97%. The percentage distribution of consumer goods industry GDP to Indonesia's GDP until 2020 is increasing every year.

The consumer goods industry has a very significant role for Indonesia's economic growth and is considered to have growth potential because it is supported by large domestic demand for consumptive products and abundant natural resources so that it should have an impact on high company value and also on stock returns that will be obtained by investors.

Fig. 1: Consumer Goods Industry Stock Return 2016 – 2021

The consumer goods industry has a very significant role for Indonesia's economic growth and is considered to have growth potential because it is supported by large domestic demand for consumptive products and abundant natural resources so that it should have an impact on high company value and also on stock returns that will be obtained by investors.

The decline that occurred in 2019 was caused by negative sentiment in the form of a plan to increase excise rates so that the demand for HMSP and GGRM company products decreased which caused the stock price of the company to decline and had an impact on stock returns obtained by investors. In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic has had a major impact on various sectors in Indonesia. The

condition of the JCI in Indonesia has decreased at the beginning of 2020 by 6.58%. The decline was followed by a decline in all sectoral indices. The consumer goods industry sector experienced the slightest decline of 17%. The sector was able to survive the COVID-19 pandemic and was able to increase production demand and sales.

There are several factors that can affect stock returns, both micro and macroeconomic. Macroeconomic factors can be in the form of inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, foreign exchange, economic growth rates, and regional stock indexes. Meanwhile, micro-economic factors can be seen from financial ratios such as return on assets, debt to asset ratios, quick ratios, and total asset turnover.

Return on Assets (ROA) is one of the profitability ratios used to measure the company's ability to generate profits by utilizing its assets (Arista, Desy, & Astohar, 2012). The greater this ratio, the better, which means that assets can get returns faster and earn profits. Measurement with ROA shows that the higher the ROA value, the better it is in providing returns to investors.

Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) is a debt ratio in measuring the ratio between total debt and total assets. In other words, asset management is influenced by the size of the company's assets financed by debt or the amount of company debt. The amount of loan capital used for investment in assets in generating profits for the company will be greater if this ratio is higher.

Quick Ratio (QR) is a ratio used to measure a company's ability to pay its short-term obligations without taking inventory into account. According to Kasmir (2014) the quick ratio is a ratio that is able to provide an overview of the company's ability to pay its short-term obligations without taking into account the inventory value of current assets. The higher the value of the quick ratio, the better the company's finances will be.

Total Asset Turnover (TATO) is used to measure the company's ability to use assets to gain profits, where this ratio is measured by comparing sales to total assets. A high TATO value illustrates the more efficient the company is in using its overall assets in generating sales. Companies that use good assets will be able to increase sales and have an effect on stock returns.

The consumer price index (CPI) is an index to calculate the average price change of a group of goods and services consumed by households within a certain period of time. The rate of increase in prices (inflation) or the rate of decline in prices (deflation) of goods and services can be shown from changes in the CPI from time to time.

Based on the background description that has been stated above, the authors are interested in conducting research on "Analysis of the Effect of Fundamental Factors and Consumer Price Index on Company Stock Return (Study on the Consumer Goods Industry Sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange 2016-2021 Period)". The

variables used are return on assets, debt to asset ratio, quick ratio, total asset turnover, and consumer price index.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Return on Asset (ROA)

This ratio shows the net profit earned by the company for each asset owned by the company. ROA is the result of the division between the company's net profit and company assets (Sari & Endri, 2019). The greater the ROA value, the greater the level of profit obtained by the company and in terms of the use of assets the company's position will be better.

The higher this ratio, the productivity of assets in obtaining net profits will be better. This will increase the attractiveness of the company to investors. Increasing the attractiveness of the company will make the company more attractive to investors. Investor interest in the company will be even greater if the attractiveness of the company increases, because the rate of return or dividends will be even greater. This will also have an impact on the stock price of the company in the capital market which will increase so that ROA will affect the company's stock price. ROA figures can be said to be good if $>2\%$.

B. Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR)

Debt to Asset Ratio is a debt ratio in measuring the comparison between total debt and total assets (Kasmir, 2014). In other words, asset management is influenced by the size of the company's assets financed by debt or the amount of company debt. The company will find it increasingly difficult to obtain additional loans because it is feared that the company will not be able to cover its debts with its assets if this ratio is high, which means that financing with more debt. Likewise, if the ratio is low, the smaller the company that is financed with debt.

C. Quick Ratio (QR)

According to Kasmir (2014), the quick ratio is a ratio that is able to provide an overview of the company's ability to pay its short-term obligations without taking into account the inventory value of current assets. The higher the value of the quick ratio, the better the company's finances will be, so that investors will have more confidence in the company. This will have an impact on increasing stock prices and resulting in an increase in stock returns.

D. Total Asset Turnover (TATO)

Total Asset Turnover (TATO) is one of the activity ratios used to determine the effectiveness of a company in managing its business. This ratio shows how efficiently the company uses its assets to generate revenue which is a determining factor in the return of operating profit. The company's operating activities require investment in current and non-current assets. This ratio represents the relationship between the company's operational level (sales) and the assets needed to support the company's operations. TATO can also be used to produce the capital needed by the company (Keown & Arthur, 2014). TATO is a ratio to calculate the effective use of total assets. A high ratio usually indicates good management, while a low ratio

should guide management in evaluating strategy, marketing, and capital expenditure (investment).

E. Consumer Price Index (CPI)

The consumer price index (CPI) is a measure of inflation by measuring the prices of goods or services that are needed or always used by consumers (Krishananti, 2018). Changes in the consumer price index for the goods or services group, whether it is an increase or decrease in the price of daily household needs, is one of the references used by the public regarding the price information (Erfit, 2018).

The consumer price index (CPI) is very important for the public because it is able to know the level of prices being traded because the CPI not only provides information for goods or services but also food, energy, and housing. The ever-changing CPI represents inflation (increase) or deflation (decrease) in the price of goods and services that can cause fluctuations (Sumantri & Lathifah, 2019). Therefore, it is very important to estimate the CPI in order to assist the government in predicting future economic conditions and to determine appropriate policies to overcome the impact of rising inflation.

F. Stock Return

Return is the result achieved by investors and can be in the form of realizations that have occurred and expected returns that are expected in the future. Investors must first evaluate the stock price to get the expected return and profit. According to Hartono (2010), stock returns are investors' returns on capital. According to Fahmi (2012), return is the profit obtained by companies, individuals, and institutions from the results of their investment policies.

Stocks are known for their high risk – high return characteristics. This means that shares are securities that not only offer high profit opportunities, but also have high risk potential. Stocks allow investors to get a return in the form of capital gains if the current stock price (Pt) is higher

than the stock price of the previous period (Pt-1), then the stock will provide benefits to investors in the form of capital gains. However, in addition to fluctuations in stock prices, investors may need to sell their shares at a selling price that is lower than the purchase price, which is called a capital loss.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The type of research used in this study is a quantitative research method with a descriptive approach. Descriptive research in this study is intended to obtain an overview and information related to the effect of Return on Assets, Debt to Asset Ratio, Quick Ratio, Total Asset Turnover, and Consumer Price Index on Stock Return. This study uses the independent variables, namely Return on Assets, Debt to Asset Ratio, Quick Ratio, Total Asset Turnover, and Consumer Price Index and the dependent variable is Stock Return. The population in this study were 63 companies in the consumer goods industry sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2016 – 2021. In this study, the sampling technique used was purposive sampling with the aim of obtaining a representative sample in accordance with predetermined criteria. The data analysis method used to solve the problem in this research is panel data regression analysis with the support of the EViews version 10 program, using data in the form of time series data and cross section.

A. Panel Data Regression Analysis

Panel data is a combination of cross-sectional and time series data (ie a set of variables observed in various categories and collected over a certain period of time (Rosadi, 2012). Cross-section data is data that is sometimes collected for many individuals and time series is data that sometimes collected for one individual. The panel data regression model can be expressed in the form of an equation as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \dots + \beta_n X_{nit} + e_{it}$$

	RS	ROA	DAR	QR	TATO	IHK
Mean	0.248341	0.080070	0.445376	1.716115	1.106955	122.7826
Median	0.035344	0.066557	0.387979	1.366308	1.018851	127.0417
Maximum	26.85714	1.037152	2.899874	7.357361	3.157465	137.6025
Minimum	-0.866154	-2.640992	0.076894	0.139330	0.294590	104.9092
Std. Dev.	1.933571	0.242761	0.316701	1.365528	0.510827	12.72100
Skewness	12.57739	-6.072868	4.414407	1.816222	1.485690	-0.422969
Kurtosis	172.5598	78.21725	31.89567	6.973369	5.918967	1.511350
Jarque-Bera	257103.8	50795.09	7987.941	253.5952	151.8078	25.65229
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000003
Sum	52.15153	16.81471	93.52900	360.3842	232.4606	25784.35
Sum Sq. Dev.	781.3876	12.31700	20.96256	389.7155	54.53744	33821.16
Observations	210	210	210	210	210	210

Table 1: Descriptive Statistical Analysis Results

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Table 1 shows the data used in this study as many as 210 samples studied during the 2016-2021 period. The stock return variable (RS) has a standard deviation value of 1.933571 (above the average value) which means that the RS has a high level of data variation. tall. The average value of RS is 0.248341, which means that in general the stock returns received are positive (experiencing profits). The maximum RS value is 26,85714 at PT. Indofarma, Tbk (INAF) in 2016 and the minimum RS value is -0.866154 at PT. Indofarma, Tbk (INAF) in 2019.

The return on asset (ROA) variable has a maximum value of 1.037152 at PT. Merck, Tbk (MERK) in 2021 and a minimum score of -2.640992 at PT. FKS Food Sejahtera, Tbk (AISA) in 2017. The standard deviation value of ROA is 0.242761 (above the average) which means that ROA has a high level of data variation. The average value or mean ROA is 0.080070, which means that during the research period, the average consumer goods industrial sector company has a profit of 8% of total assets. This shows the level of effectiveness of companies in the consumer goods industry sector to generate profits in managing the funds invested in overall assets.

The variable debt to asset ratio (DAR) has a maximum value of 2.899874 at PT. FKS Food Sejahtera, Tbk (AISA) in 2018 and a minimum score of 0.076894 at PT. The Herbal and Pharmaceutical Industry of Sido Muncul, Tbk (SIDO) in 2016. The standard deviation of the DAR value is 0.316701 (below the average) which means that the DAR has a low level of data variation. The average value or mean DAR is 0.445376, which means that the average consumer goods industry company has a debt of 0.445376 times the assets owned by the company.

The quick ratio (QR) variable has a maximum value of 7.357361 at PT. Delta Jakarta, Tbk (DLTA) in 2017 and a minimum score of 0.139330 at PT. FKS Food Sejahtera, Tbk (AISA) in 2018. The standard deviation value of QR is 1.365528 (below the average) which means that QR has a low level of data variation. The average value or mean QR is 1.716115.

The variable Total Asset Turnover (TATO) has a maximum value of 3.157465 at PT. Wilmar Cahaya Indonesia, Tbk (CEKA) in 2021 and a minimum score of 0.294590 at PT. Martina Berto, Tbk (MBTO) in 2020. The standard deviation of TATO is 0.510827 (below the average) which means that TATO has a low level of data variation. The average value or mean TATO is 1.106955, which means that every Rp. 1 of the company's assets can generate Rp. 1.106955 in sales.

The Consumer Price Index (CPI) variable has a maximum value of 137.6025 at PT. Langgeng Makmur Industri, Tbk (LMPI) in 2019 and a minimum score of 104,9092 at PT. Langgeng Makmur Industri, Tbk (LMPI) in 2020. The standard deviation of the CPI is 12.72100 (below the average) which means that the CPI has a low level of data variation. The average value or the mean CPI is 122.7826.

B. Model Selection Test

a) Chow Test

The hypotheses in the Chow Test are as follows:

H0: common effect model

H1: fixed effect model

If the probability value of the cross section $F > 0.05$, then the model chosen is the common effect model, but if the cross section $F < 0.05$, then the model chosen is the fixed effect model.

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests			
Equation: Untitled			
Test cross-section fixed effects			
Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.204713	(34,170)	0.2200

Table 2: Chow Test Results

Based on Table 2 above, it can be seen that the probability value of the cross section F is $0.2200 > 0.05$, so that the hypothesis H0 is accepted and H1 is rejected, which means that the right model to be used between the common effect model and the fixed effect model is the common effect model. Furthermore, it is necessary to carry out the next test, namely the Hausman test to choose between the fixed effect model and the random effect model.

b) Hausman Test

The hypothesis in the Hausman test is as follows:

H0: random effect model

H1: fixed effect model

If the probability value of the random cross section is > 0.05 , then the selected model is a random effect model, but if the random cross section is < 0.05 , then the model chosen is the fixed effect model.

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test			
Equation: Untitled			
Test cross-section random effects			
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	0.000000	5	1.0000

Table 3: Hausman Test Results

c) Lagrange Multiplier Test

The hypothesis in the Lagrange Multiplier Test is as follows:

- H0: common effect model
- H1: random effect model

If the probability value of Breusch-Pagan > 0.05, then the model chosen is the common effect model, but if the probability value of Breusch-Pagan is < 0.05, then the model chosen is the random effect model.

Lagrange Multiplier Tests for Random Effects			
Null hypotheses: No effects			
Alternative hypotheses: Two-sided (Breusch-Pagan) and one-sided (all others) alternatives			
	Test Hypothesis		
	Cross-section	Time	Both
Breusch-Pagan	0.262122 (0.6087)	0.131282 (0.7171)	0.393404 (0.5305)

Table 4: Lagrange Multiplier Test Results

Based on Table 4 above, it can be seen that the Breusch-Pagan probability value is 0.5305 > 0.05, so the hypothesis H0 is accepted and H1 is rejected, which means that the right model to be used between the common effect model and the random effect model is the common effect model.

C. Conclusion Model Selection

Based on the panel data regression model selection test that has been carried out through the Chow test, Hausman test, and Lagrange multiplier test, it can be concluded that the common effect model is the most appropriate to be used to estimate and analyze the influence of fundamental factors and consumer price index on stock returns of industrial sector companies. consumer goods listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the period 2016 – 2021. The regression results using the common effect model are as follows:

Dependent Variable: RS					
Method: Panel Least Squares					
Date: 06/21/22 Time: 22:10					
Sample: 2016 2021					
Periods included: 6					
Cross-sections included: 35					
Total panel (balanced) observations: 210					
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	
C	1.375010	1.364667	1.007579	0.0314	
ROA	1.823032	0.616198	1.733567	0.0392	
DAR	1.835648	0.537456	1.791969	0.0293	
QR	1.824847	0.116084	1.754813	0.0283	
TATO	1.523448	0.270699	1.586620	0.0931	
IHK	1.726046	0.010661	1.767110	0.0313	
R-squared	0.008160	Mean dependent var		0.248000	
Adjusted R-squared	-0.016149	S.D. dependent var		1.933687	
S.E. of regression	1.949238	Akaike info criterion		4.200910	
Sum squared resid	775.1041	Schwarz criterion		4.296541	
Log likelihood	-435.0955	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.239570	
F-statistic	0.335687	Durbin-Watson stat		1.290015	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.890933				

Table 5: Common Effect Model Regression Results

Based on the results of the random effects regression model shown in Table 5, the results of the regression model equation between the dependent variable and the independent variable are obtained as follows:

$$RS = 1.375010 + 1.823032 (ROA) + 1.835648 (DAR) + 1.824847 (QR) + 1.523448 (TATO) + 1.726046 (CPI)$$

D. Classic Assumption Test

a) Normality Test

According to Ghazali (2016), if the significance probability value is greater than 0.05, then the data is normally distributed. However, if the significance probability value is less than 0.05, then the data is not normally distributed.

Fig. 2: Normality Test Results

Based on Figure 2 above, it can be seen that the probability value is $0.000000 < 0.05$. These results indicate that this study has data that are not normally distributed. According to Gujarati (2009), if you have a large enough sample size or a large number of observations, then the assumption of normality is not very important. According to Ghasemi & Zahediasl (2012), with a large enough sample size (>30 or 40), data that are not normally

distributed will not cause big problems, so the data distribution can be ignored.

b) Multicollinearity Test

If the correlation value is greater than 0.80, it is suspected that there is multicollinearity in the model. A good regression model should not show a correlation between each variable.

	ROA	DAR	QR	TATO	IHK
ROA	1.000000	-0.405819	0.145642	0.151343	0.003569
DAR	-0.405819	1.000000	-0.507382	-0.025253	0.042670
QR	0.145642	-0.507382	1.000000	-0.111941	0.004660
TATO	0.151343	-0.025253	-0.111941	1.000000	0.086261
IHK	0.003569	0.042670	0.004660	0.086261	1.000000

Table 6: Multicollinearity Test Results

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that there is no correlation value greater than 0.80. This shows that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables ROA, DAR, QR, TATO, and CPI.

c) Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity test in this study uses the white method to detect the presence or absence of heteroscedasticity by looking at the probability value. The results of the heteroscedasticity test can be seen in the following table:

Heteroskedasticity Test: White			
Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity			
F-statistic	0.238345	Prob. F(14,130)	0.9998
Obs*R-squared	5.166257	Prob. Chi-Square(14)	0.9996
Scaled explained SS	418.5599	Prob. Chi-Square(14)	0.0000

Table 7: Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Based on Table 7 it can be seen that the prob value. chi-square has a result of more than 0.05, which is 0.9996,

it can be concluded that there is no symptom of heteroscedasticity.

d) Autocorrelation Test

In this study, the autocorrelation test used the Breusch-Godfrey test to identify the presence or

absence of autocorrelation. The results of the autocorrelation test can be seen from the following table:

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:			
Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at up to 2 lags			
F-statistic	0.058197	Prob. F(2,138)	0.9435
Obs*R-squared	0.120933	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.9413

Table 8: Autocorrelation Test Results

Based on Table 8, it can be seen that the prob value. chi-square has a result greater than 0.05, which is 0.9413, it can be concluded that there is no autocorrelation.

E. Hypothesis test

a) Partial Test (t-test)

• Effect of Return on Assets (ROA) on Stock Return

Variable	t-Statistic	Prob.
ROA	1.733567	0.0392

Table 9: ROA Hypothesis Test Results

Based on Table 9, the results of the panel data regression analysis partially show the t-count result of 1.733567 with a probability value of 0.0392 < 0.05. While the t-table with $\alpha=5\%$ and $df(n-k-1) = (210-5-1) = 204$, then

the t-table $(0.05;204) = 1.652357$. Thus, t-count is greater than t-table, which means that the Return on Assets (ROA) variable has a significant effect on stock returns.

• Effect of Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) on Stock Return

Variable	t-Statistic	Prob.
DAR	1.791969	0.0293

Table 10: DAR Hypothesis Test Results

Based on Table 10, the results of the panel data regression analysis partially show the t-count result of 1.791969 with a probability value of 0.0293 < 0.05. While the t-table with $\alpha=5\%$ and $df(n-k-1) = (210-5-1) = 204$, then

the t-table $(0.05;204) = 1.652357$. Thus, t-count is greater than t-table, which means the variable Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) has a significant effect on stock returns.

• Effect of Quick Ratio (QR) on Stock Return

Variable	t-Statistic	Prob.
QR	1.754813	0.0283

Table 11: QR Hypothesis Test Results

Based on Table 11, the results of the panel data regression analysis partially show the t-count result of 1.754813 with a probability value of 0.0283 < 0.05. While the t-table with $\alpha=5\%$ and $df(n-k-1) = (210-5-1) = 204$, then

the t-table $(0.05;204) = 1.652357$. Thus, t-count is greater than t-table, which means that the Quick Ratio (CR) variable has a significant effect on stock returns.

• Effect of Total Asset Turnover (TATO) on Stock Return

Variable	t-Statistic	Prob.
TATO	1.586620	0.0931

Table 12: TATO Hypothesis Test Results

Based on Table 12, the results of the panel data regression analysis partially show the t-count result of 1.586620 with a probability value of 0.0931 > 0.05. While the t-table with $\alpha=5\%$ and $df(n-k-1) = (210-5-1) = 204$, then

the t-table $(0.05;204) = 1.652357$. Thus, the t-count is smaller than the t-table, which means that the Total Asset Turnover (TATO) variable has no significant effect on stock returns.

• Effect of Consumer Price Index (CPI) on Stock Return

Variable	t-Statistic	Prob.
IHK	1.767110	0.0313

Table 13: CPI Hypothesis Test Results

Based on Table 13, the results of the panel data regression analysis partially show the t-count result of 1.767110 with a probability value of 0.0313 < 0.05. While the t-table with $\alpha=5\%$ and $df(n-k-1) = (210-5-1) = 204$, then the t-table $(0.05;204) = 1.652357$. Thus, t-count is greater than t-table, which means that the Consumer Price Index (CPI) variable has a significant effect on stock returns.

Based on the partial test or t-test that has been carried out, of the five independent variables that affect the stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector, there are four variables that have a significant influence, namely the return on asset (ROA) variable, debt to asset ratio (DAR), quick ratio (QR), and the consumer price index (CPI). While one independent variable, namely total asset turnover (TATO) has no significant effect.

b) F test

If the calculated F value > F table, then the independent variable simultaneously affects or affects the dependent variable. However, if F count < F table, then there is no independent variable that affects or affects the dependent variable.

R-squared	0.081610
Adjusted R-squared	0.161491
F-statistic	2.335687
Prob(F-statistic)	0.039093

Table 14: F-Test Results

Based on Table 14 above, it shows that the calculated F value is 2.335687, while the F table with a significance level of 5% and $df1 = 5-1 = 4$ and $df2 = 210-5 = 205$, the F table value is 2.26. Thus F count > F table (2.335687 > 2.26) so it can be concluded that the independent variables together have a significant effect on the dependent variable. Then the probability value (prob.) is 0.039093 which is smaller than the 0.05 significance level, which means that the ROA, DAR, QR, TATO, and CPI variables simultaneously or simultaneously have a significant and significant effect on stock returns.

c) Coefficient of Determination

The coefficients of determination of ROA, DAR, QR, TATO, and CPI can be seen in Table 14. Based on Table 14, the Adjusted R-Square value is 0.161491 which indicates that the percentage of the independent variable on the dependent variable is 16.14% while the remaining 83.86% is influenced by other factors. other.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Effect of ROA on Stock Return

Based on empirical research findings, the return on assets (ROA) variable has a significant effect on stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector in 2016-2021. This shows that if the return on assets (ROA) increases, then the stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector will also increase. will increase. Conversely, if the return on assets decreases, it will reduce the stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector. These results are in accordance with research conducted by Moch.Fathony, Khaq, & Endri (2020), Mayuni (2018), Indah (2016), Abdel, Nu'aimat, & Dahmash (2012), and Gunadi G. G (2015). However, this result contradicts the research conducted by Setiyono & Amanah (2016) and Risdiyanto & Suhermin (2016).

B. Effect of DAR on Stock Return

Based on empirical research findings, the debt to asset ratio (DAR) variable has a significant effect on stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector in 2016-2021. These results are in accordance with research conducted by Andriani (2020), Widayanti & Haryanto (2013), Widyawati (2013) and Kurniawati & Kustianingsih (2021). However, these results contradict the research conducted by Gunawan & Hardyani (2014), Oktanugroho (2012), and Hidayat & Indrihastuti (2019).

C. Effect of QR on Stock Return

Based on empirical research findings, the quick ratio (QR) variable has a significant effect on stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector in 2016-2021. These results are in accordance with research conducted by Agustin & Taswan (2017), Dewi & Fajri (2019), and Farida, Ida, & Camela (2018). However, these results contradict the research conducted by Sunaryo (2020) and Handayani, Herdiyana, & Azhar (2019).

D. Effect of TATO on Stock Return

Based on empirical research findings, the Total Asset Turnover (TATO) variable has no significant effect on stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector in 2016-2021. This means that the company's ability to optimize its activities effectively and efficiently has no effect on investor interest in buying company shares. This is because high sales do not guarantee high profits to be generated by the company. The sales value has not been deducted by debt, interest, and other costs in the company's financial statements. These results are in accordance with research conducted by Abdullah (2016), Andansari, Raharjo, & Andini (2016), Azizah (2018), and Bisara & Amanah (2015). However, this result contradicts research conducted by Khotimah & Murtaqi (2015), Dewi P. (2016), and Sausan, Korawijayanti, & Ciptaningtias (2020).

E. Effect of CPI on Stock Return

Based on empirical research findings, the Consumer Price Index (CPI) variable has a significant effect on stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector in 2016-2021. The Consumer Price Index is the weighted average price of goods and services consumed by the public. The increase in the Consumer Price Index was due to an increase in the price of goods due to the increase in the cost of producing goods. The increase in the price of goods can reduce the demand for goods sold by companies in the trading sector, as a result, the company's income (operating profit) decreases. The decrease in operating profit resulted in a decrease in the interest of investors and the public in investing in stocks in the trading sector, resulting in a decrease in stock prices and stock returns. These results are in accordance with research conducted by Kuwornu (2012), Kudryavtsev, Levav, & Shahrabani (2012), and Adusei (2014). However, this result contradicts research conducted by Arif, Achsani, & Sasongko (2013), Riantani & Tambunan (2013), and Suryanto & Kesuma (2013) proving that inflation seen from the CPI has no effect on stock returns.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusions

Based on the results of research on consumer goods industrial sector companies on the IDX for the 2016-2021 period, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Return on Assets (ROA) has a significant effect on stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector listed on the IDX for the 2016-2021 period. This is indicated by the t-count distribution of $1.733567 > t$ table 1.652357 with a significance level of 5% and a probability value of $0.0392 < 0.05$
- Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) has a significant effect on stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector listed on the IDX for the period 2016-2021. This is indicated by the t-count distribution of $1.791969 > t$ table 1.652357 with a significance level of 5% and a probability value of $0.0293 < 0.05$
- Quick Ratio (QR) has a significant effect on stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector listed on the IDX for the period 2016-2021. This is indicated by the t arithmetic distribution of $1.754813 > t$ table 1.652357 with a significance level of 5% and a probability value of $0.0283 < 0.05$
- Total Asset Turnover (TATO) has no significant effect on stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector listed on the IDX for the 2016-2021 period. This is indicated by the t-count distribution of $1.586620 < t$ table 1.652357 with a significance level of 5% and a probability value of $0.0931 > 0.05$
- The Consumer Price Index (CPI) has a significant effect on stock returns of companies in the consumer goods industry sector listed on the IDX for the 2016-2021 period. This is indicated by the t-count distribution of Quick Ratio (QR), Total Asset Turnover (TATO), and Consumer Price Index (CPI) together or simultaneously have a significant and significant effect on stock returns.

B. Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions regarding the variables including ROA, DAR, QR, TATO, and the Consumer Price Index on stock returns in companies in the consumer goods industry sector, the authors try to convey some suggestions for consideration including the following:

- For investors, this research is expected to be used as an illustration of how the condition of the consumer goods industrial sector during the 2016-2021 period and can be used as material to assess the consumer goods industrial sector in Indonesia in making decisions according to the needs of each party.
- For academics, this research is expected to be useful for those who want to know how much influence ROA, DAR, QR, TATO, and the Consumer Price Index have on stock returns of the consumer goods industry sector in the 2016-2021 period. In particular, it is recommended for further research to use a longer and more recent observation period. The addition of the number of research samples with a longer and more recent observation period is more likely to produce results that are closer to the real condition

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